

DEGRADATION BEHAVIOR OF AMINE CURED EPOXY RESIN AND FRP IN ACID SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACTS

Corrosion behavior of bisphenol A-type epoxy resin cured with 1,8-p-menthandiamine was studied by immersion test in several acid solutions at 80°C.

In HCl, H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄ solutions, large weight gain was observed, and it reached the constant level. In CH₃COOH and HNO₃ solutions, on the other hand, reduction of weight and flexural strength were observed. In HNO₃ solution, especially, severe degradation occurred and the cured resin was decomposed completely.

The severe corrosion of the amine cured epoxy resin in HNO₃ showed the possibility as the method to separate the glass fiber from the matrix resin of FRP in the process of waste treatment. To make sure the expectation, the immersion test of FRP in acids were also carried out.

INTRODUCTION

FRP have been widely used in industry because of their excellent mechanical and chemical properties and also economical point of view. At present, corrosion resistant FRP are in use as large tanks, vessels and pipings in chemical plant.

However FRP are corroded severely depending on the combination of matrix resin systems and environments[1-4]. Amine cured epoxy resin shows good corrosion resistance in alkaline solutions, but shows poor resistance in acid solutions[2].

With increase of FRP applications, recently, much attention is now focused on the disposal of waste FRP[5-7]. Almost all types of method have disposed of the waste FRP together with matrix resin and glass fiber because it was difficult to separate the fiber from the matrix. Then poor corrosion resistance of the resin can be expected to be useful as the separation method.

In this study, corrosion behavior of amine cured epoxy resin as the matrix of FRP in several acid solutions was studied, and also the possibility as the method of disposal and recycling of FRP were discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Resin used was a bisphenol-A type epoxy resin cured with 1,8-p-menthandiamine(MDA-EP), and the crosslinked structure was shown in Fig.1. FRP used were glass mat and cloth reinforced MDA-EP of which glass content were 54.1wt.% and 55.3wt.% respectively.

Fig.1 Epoxy resin cured with MDA.(MDA-EP)

Immersion tests were carried out with plate type specimens of 25x60mm and 2mm thickness at 80 °C. Test environments used were HCl, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄, CH₃COOH and HNO₃ solutions.

After immersion, specimens were removed from the environments, then rinsed with water lightly and left in air for 1 hour, and were weighed (wet weight). The specimens were also weighed after complete drying at 50°C (dry weight). Flexural strength of immersed specimens were measured at room temperature with 40mm span. Observation of specimen appearance, discussion with infrared spectroscopy (IR), x-ray microanalyzer (XAM) and size exclusion chromatography (SEC) were further performed to make clear the corrosion mechanism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(a) Corrosion behavior of resin

Figs.2 & 3 show the change of weight at wet and dry conditions in acid solutions and NaOH solution for comparison. Linear relationship between wet weight and square root of immersion time($t^{1/2}$) can be observed at early stage of immersion in H₂SO₄, HCl and CH₃COOH solutions. This means the diffusion of solution into the resin obeys Fick's law. In H₃PO₄ solution, different mechanism is considered because large and accelerative weight gain is observed. In HNO₃ solution, on the other hand, weight loss is observed from 30~40 hours immersion, and the resin is dissolved completely after about 100 hours immersion. Almost the same behavior can be recognized in dry weight (Fig.3), but slight dissolution can be expected in CH₃COOH solution.

Figs.4 & 5 show the retention of flexural strength (RFS) by immersion at wet and dry conditions. The flexural strength decrease by immersion, but the strength recover to the original level by drying at early period of immersion in H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄ and HCl. This means that the decrease of strength at early period in wet condition is due to the physical degradation. On the other hand, severe decrease of strength can be observed from early period in HNO₃ and CH₃COOH in which dissolution of resin was observed in Fig.3.

Fig.2 Weight change of resins by immersion into environments.(2mol/l, wet weight)

Fig.3 Weight change of resins by immersion into environments.(2mol/l, dry weight)

Fig. 4 Change of retention of flexural strength of resins.(2mol/l, wet condition)

Fig. 5 Change of retention of flexural strength.(2mol/l, dry condition)

The change of specimens thickness were also measured, and the thickness decreased only in HNO₃ solution, but increased in the other acid solutions, especially large swelling was observed in H₃PO₄ solution.

After immersion into CH₃COOH solution, many cracks were observed at the specimen surface, and the cracks partially disappeared by heat treatment at 100°C, 30 hours. Therefore the development of craze can be considered to be one reason of decrease of strength in CH₃COOH solution.

In alkaline solution (NaOH soln.), excellent corrosion resistance can be recognized from the results shown in Figs.2 & 4.

(b) Corrosion mechanism of resin

The large weight gain observed in H₂SO₄ and HCl etc. are due to the formation of tertiary amine salt at amine group by following reaction.

where R₃N, HX and (R₃NH⁺)X⁻ are amine, acid and amine salt respectively. When all of the amines in the resin are converted to amine salt, the weight gain reaches to equilibrium level (ex. in H₂SO₄). The severe distortion is produced around the amine salt and the stability of C-N bonds which are usually chemically stable decreases, then the scission of the bonds occur and the strength decreases gradually.

In HNO₃ solution, color of the specimen changed to yellow and NO_x gas generated during immersion. And the IR analysis for corrosion product observed on the specimen surface and residue in solution showed the new peaks of transmittance at 1700cm⁻¹, 1350cm⁻¹ and 900cm⁻¹ on IR spectrum as shown in Fig.6. These peaks correspond to carbonyl group, nitro group and carboxylic acid respectively. At the same time, the peak of aliphatic ether around at 1020cm⁻¹ disappeared. These results show that the scission of not only the C-N bonds but also of ether

bonds which are formed by polymerization with a pair of main chain occur. Thus, characteristic severe corrosion behavior in HNO_3 solution shown in Fig.2~Fig.5 can be explained.

Above mentioned corrosion mechanism in HNO_3 solution was supported also by the discussion with size exclusion chromatography (SEC). The liquate outs from resin into HNO_3 solution after 100 and 1000 hours immersion were extracted with ethyl acetate, then solutes obtained after evaporation were dissolved in tetrahydroflan (THF), and then analyzed by SEC. Fig.7 shows the molecular weight distribution of solutes in the THF solution and uncured EP measured by SEC. Uncured EP shows two peaks which correspond to monomer and dimer compounds. The solutes in the solution, on the other hand, have very sharp molecular weight distribution independently of immersion time, and have slightly larger molecular weight than that of uncured EP. This means that the corrosion product as solutes would be a simple and stable compound such as an oxidized and/or nitrated bisphenol A. Such the corrosion behavior of MDA-EP in HNO_3 solution suggests the possibility as a separation method of glass fiber from matrix resin and chemical recycle of resin.

Fig.6 IR spectra. (a) before immersion, (b) corrosion products after 100 hours (c) residue in solution after 1000 hours. (2mol/l , HNO_3)

Fig. 7 SEC chromatograms of uncured EP and solutes after immersion. (2mol/l , HNO_3)

(c) Corrosion behavior of FRP

The immersion tests of mat and cloth FRP were carried out. Figs.8 & 9 show the dry weight change of FRP specimens in several environments. Almost the same behavior as resin shown in Fig.3 can be recognized. Fig.10 shows the comparison of the weight change of neat resin and that of matrix in FRP which were calculated by burning the immersed specimens. Quite equal rates of weight loss of resin can be observed in neat resin and the FRP, this means the glass fiber showed no effect on corrosion behavior of matrix resin in FRP. Figs.8~10 also show that all resin are dissolved after about 700~800 hours in 2mol/l HNO₃ solutions.

Fig.8 Weight change of mat FRP by immersion into several environments. (2mol/l, dry condition)

Fig.9 Weight change of cloth FRP by immersion into several environments. (2mol/l, dry condition)

Fig.10 Comparison of weight change of resins in neat resin and FRP specimens. (2mol/l HNO₃, dry condition)

The dissolution rate increased with increase of the concentration of HNO₃ as shown in Fig.11, and the resin was dissolved completely only after 100 hours in 4mol/l solution. Complete dissolution of resin can be also recognized by Fig.12 which shows the appearances of FRP specimens immersed into HNO₃ solution. By comparison with the results in 3 or 4mol/l solutions shown in Fig.11 and glass contents of FRP, however, it can be noticed that slight dissolution of E-glass was accompanied.

Fig.11 Effect of concentration of HNO₃ on weight change of cloth FRP. (dry condition)

Fig.12 Appearances of FRP specimens after immersion into HNO₃ solution.
(a) mat FRP (4mol/l, 100 hours), (b) cloth FRP (2mol/l, 700 hours).

CONCLUSIONS

Corrosion behavior and mechanism of amine cured epoxy resin (MDA-EP) in several acid solutions have discussed in detail.

The common mechanism for the degradation of MDA-EP was the scission of C-N bonds which followed the formation of tertiary amine salt. The large weight gain was recognized in general acids by the formation of amine salt. In HNO₃ solution, however, the scission of ether bonds occurred from the early period of immersion, then severe dissolution of the resin was caused.

The same severe corrosion of matrix resin in FRP was observed and the possibility as the separation method of matrix and glass fiber was shown. The SEC analysis showed resin dissolved into HNO₃ as a simple compound, this suggests the possibility of chemical recycle of matrix resin too.

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